

Sample metadata for manuscript “Accurate Identification of Fly Species in Forensic, Medical and Veterinary Entomology using Wing Venation Patterns”

Table 1 shows the collection location of specimens by their image index and the collection from which the specimens come from.

Species	Image index	Location	Collection
<i>A.gressitti</i>	1-13	Malaysia	1
<i>B.karyni</i>	1-20	Malaysia	1
<i>C.albiceps</i>	1-100	Spain	2
<i>C.albiceps_mutant</i>	1-100	Spain	2
<i>C.bezziana</i>	1-4	Africa	3
	5	India	3
	6-21	Java	3
	22-23	Malaysia	3
	24-29	Sulawesi	3
	30-37	Sumatra	3
	38-57	Sumba	3
<i>C.megacephala</i>	1-16	Java	3
	17-33	Kalimantan	3
	34	Lombok	3
	35-43	Malaysia	1
	44-59	Southeast Sumatra	3
	60-61	Sulawesi	3
	62-77	Sumatra	3
	78-81	West Papua	3
82	West Timor	3	
<i>C.nigripes</i>	1-10	Malaysia	1
<i>C.rufifacies</i>	1-6	Malaysia	1
	7-26	Sumatra	3
	27-37	Sumba	3
<i>C.vicina</i>	1-100	Spain	2
<i>L.alba</i>	1-10	Malaysia	1
<i>L.sericata</i>	1-100	Spain	2
<i>S.aquila</i>	1-19	Malaysia	1
<i>S.nudiseta</i>	1-100	Spain	2
<i>S.princeps</i>	1-11	Malaysia	1

Table 1: Collector and location information of specimens in the study

Note:

(1) The species name *S.aquila* (*Sarcophaga aquila*) has been changed to *Zulisca alba* owing to recent taxonomic revision (Kurahashi, Tan & Leh, 2021).

(2) Collection 1 is contributed by Dr. Siew Hwa Tan; Collection 2 by Dr. Tania Ivorra; Collection 3 by Dr. April Hari Wardhana.

Reference:

Kurahashi H, Tan SH, Leh MU (2021) Keys to the flesh flies of Sarawak, East Malaysia, with descriptions of two new genera and eight new species (Diptera: Sarcophagidae). *Med Entomol Zool* 72:119-175. <https://doi.org/10.7601/mez.72.119>